

Potentiometric Studies on Electron Transfer Reactions of Anodically generated Manganese(III) Sulphate in Aqueous H₂SO₄-HOAc and Manganese(III) Acetate in Aqueous Acetic Acid : Oxidation of Semicarbazide and Semicarbazones

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Manganese(III) sulphate in aqueous sulphuric acid and manganese(III) acetate in aqueous acetic acid have been prepared by electrolytic methods with high current efficiency. The nature of the manganese(III) formed is elucidated spectrophotometrically. Condition for potentiometric determination of semicarbazide and its derivatives under different reaction conditions have been investigated. Hydrazinium sulphate or hydroquinone is employed as back-titrant. The number of electrons in these oxidations differed, depending on the nature of the molecule and the reaction condition. The free radical nature of the reaction intermediate is demonstrated. Manganese(III) sulphate and manganese(III) acetate oxidation of semicarbazide and its derivatives in aqueous H₂SO₄ or aqueous HOAc yielded different results, probably because of the changes in the coordination environment of manganese(III).

The biological role of manganese has stimulated studies relating to the interaction of Mn^{III} with a broad spectrum of electron donors^{1,2}. Quite recently we have used Mn^{III} systems for the oxidation of amino acids³, thiosemicarbazides^{4,5}, thiocyanates^{6,7}, pyridoxinehydrochloride^{8,9}, benzoylhydrazines⁷ and aroxyacetylhydrazines¹⁰. In the latter case, it was observed that the number of electrons involved is altered by varying solvent composition, thereby showing the selectivity of Mn^{III} as an oxidising agent. The aim of the present work was to understand how the changes in the coordination environment of manganese(III) can influence its redox behaviour and the mechanism of the related reactions. With this objective, electrolytically released manganese(III) sulphate in aqueous sulphuric acid and manganese(III) acetate in aqueous acetic acid have been employed for the oxidation of semicarbazide and semicarbazone derivatives. Semicarbazides and semicarbazones are an important class of hydrazine derivatives known for their biological activities and synthetic applications¹¹.

Results and Discussion

It has been established that Mn^{III} solution can be stabilised by the increase of acidity, increase of Mn^{II} concentration or complex formation². Manganese(III) sulphate was stable for at least one month at [H⁺] > 5.0 mol dm⁻³. At lower concentration of H₂SO₄, Mn^{III} deteriorated at a faster rate but its stability could be increased by adding larger amount of Mn^{II}. Manganese(III) sulphate at concentration of less than 0.002 mol dm⁻³ was found to be stable in aqueous H₂SO₄-HOAc (overall concentration of H₂SO₄, 2.5 mol dm⁻³, and HOAc, 20–60%, v/v). Manganese(III) acetate solution was stable in acetic acid-water mixture containing acetic acid above 75% (v/v) for about 48 h, thereafter disproportionation slowly set in and black particles of MnO₂ were formed. At lower percentage of acetic acid, manganese(III) acetate deteriorated at a faster rate, but its stability, could be increased by adding higher amount of manganese(II) acetate. It has been established that manganese(III) in aqueous

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acid solution contained $Mn^{3+}aq.$ and $Mn(OH)^{2+}aq.$ as reactive species¹². Electronic absorption spectra of both $Mn^{3+}aq.$ and $MnOH^{2+}aq.$ have been shown to be similar both in the visible and uv region³. Kinetic study³ has shown that $MnOH^{2+}aq.$ is more reactive than $Mn^{3+}aq.$

Fresh solution of manganese(III) sulphate was always prepared and used immediately after cessation of the electrolysis, to eliminate any reaction due to $Mn(OH)_2$ that could be present in aged solution. Molar absorption coefficient at wavelength 490 nm varied as function of $[H^+]$ (ϵ 131–110 $dm^3 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$ at $[H^+] = 1.28$ – $2.98 mol dm^{-3}$). Manganese(III) sulphate in aqueous H_2SO_4 -HOAc medium showed similar absorption pattern with λ_{max} at 490 nm, but a slight increase in molar absorption coefficient was observed.

Electronic absorption spectra of the freshly prepared manganese(III) acetate at different acetic acid and KOAc concentrations were recorded. It was found that a manganic complex is formed in the presence of higher concentration of acetate, possibly the one in which water ligand is replaced by acetate ion¹³, the evidence being the change in the visible spectra of manganic acetate which showed intense absorption at 420 nm. This was a clear indication that the reactive species in manganese(III) acetate in aqueous acetic acid system is the undissociated $Mn(OAc)_3$ or the acetato complex $Mn(OAc)_4^-$.

The formal redox potential of the Mn^{III} - M^{II} couple under the conditions employed in these studies as determined in our previous studies, were 1.52 and 1.16 V respectively, for manganese(III) sulphate and manganese(III) acetate.

Oxidations by manganese(III) sulphate in aqueous H_2SO_4 or H_2SO_4 -HOAc medium : Hydrazinium sulphate has been introduced as a back-titrant. A reproducible one-electron stoichiometry observed could be represented as :

The statistical data obtained are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The redox reactions of manganese(III) sulphate

with semicarbazide hydrochloride and its derivatives are stoichiometric and involve three electrons which may be represented as

The unidentified inorganic product owing to greater degree of resonance stabilisation involved, does not show evidence of undergoing further oxidation. The free radical nature of these reactions was established by polymerisation studies. It was found that the reacting mixture under less drastic condition, i.e. at 0°, initiates polymerisation of monomers like acrylonitrile and methyl methacrylate. As neither of the reacting species, semicarbazide hydrochloride or manganese(III) sulphate, did this when added to an aqueous mixture of these monomers, it could be assumed that the redox steps produced some free radicals which were capable of inducing polymerisations. Further, the polymerisation product of methyl methacrylate monomer from the above reaction, answered the Lassignes test confirming the presence of nitrogen containing end-group.

The ir spectra of the above polymer showed a peak at 1730 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of ester carbonyl group and another peak at 1429 cm^{-1} which is characteristic of unsymmetrical $-N=N-$ bond.

TABLE 1—POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF SEMICARBAZIDE HYDROCHLORIDE AND SEMICARBAZONE DERIVATIVES IN H₂SO₄–HOAc MEDIUM

Compd.	Range studied mg	Medium		Electrons participating in reaction		Maximum error %
		H ₂ SO ₄ mol dm ⁻³	HOAc %(v/v)	Calcd.	Found ± SD ^a	
		Semicarbazide hydrochloride	0.55–13.94	1.25 1.50 2.00 2.50 3.00 2.50 2.50 2.50	– – – – – 5.0 10.0 20.0 30.0	
Propionaldehyde semicarbazone ^b	0.58–14.40	2.50	20.0	5.0	5.00 ± 0.02	0.87
Acetone semicarbazone	0.58–14.40	2.50	20.0	3.0	2.95 ± 0.02	1.17
Acetophenone semicarbazone	0.18–4.52	2.50	20.0	3.0	3.03 ± 0.01	1.25
Benzaldehyde semicarbazone	0.42–8.31	2.50	20.0	3.0	2.97 ± 0.01	0.35
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde semicarbazone	0.49–4.93	2.50	20.0	3.0	2.63 ± 0.01	0.81
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde semicarbazone	0.21–5.20	2.50	20.0	2.0	1.82 ± 0.01	0.98
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde semicarbazone	0.21–5.20	2.50	20.0	2.0	1.86 ± 0.02	1.54

^aStandard deviations for 6 determinations. ^bDirect titration at 343 K.

The same stoichiometries hold good when the reactions were carried out in a medium containing overall H₂SO₄ (2.5 mol dm⁻³) and HOAc upto 30% (v/v). However, when HOAc was above 30% (v/v) the reactions did not yield reproducible values.

In case of propionaldehyde semicarbazone, direct titration was preferred in order to demonstrate two-stage oxidation process, namely, 3-electron oxidation of the semicarbazide moiety with the regeneration of the propionaldehyde. At elevated temperature (70°) propionaldehyde was further oxidised to propionic acid. But the oxidation reaction rate of this aldehyde was sufficiently slow so that this determination was possible only when the analytical conditions were adequately controlled. The reaction can be represented as

Semicarbazones of acetone, acetophenone, benzaldehyde and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde underwent three-electron change oxidation. The regenerated ketones or aldehydes did not react further under the experimental conditions and were isolated in the ether extracts of the reaction mixture and identified as 2,4-dinitrophen-

nylhydrazones isolable upto 90%. A different trend was observed in case of semicarbazones of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde and *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde. These substrates undergo oxidation by donating upto two electrons only,

Previous researches showed that electron transfer to Mn^{III} involves the formation of $\text{N}-\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}$ intermediate¹⁴. The electron transfer to Mn^{III} is facilitated by the electron-donating groups or retarded by electron-withdrawing groups. It appears that in such cases the number of electrons transferred in the redox process depends on the electron density in the aromatic ring. As can be seen here, Mn^{III} could extract only two electrons from one molecule of nitrobenzaldehyde semicarbazone.

Oxidations by manganese(III) acetate in aqueous acetic acid: As can be seen from Table 2, the number of electrons exchanged in the oxidations of semicarbazide hydrochloride by manganese(III) acetate in acetic acid-water medium is two.

The oxidation products of the reaction are supported by literature^{14,15}. Similar scheme can be envisaged for the reaction between manganese(III) acetate and semicarbazone derivatives,

$\text{R} = \text{CH}_3, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$

$\text{R}' = \text{H}, \text{CH}_3 \text{ or } \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$

The regenerated aldehyde or ketone as the case may be, was identified as its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone isolable upto 90% yields. Since the the electron transfer to Mn^{III} is retarded by electron-withdrawing groups, oxidation of semicarbazone of nitrobenzaldehyde was

very sluggish.

With semicarbazones of hydroxybenzaldehydes the regenerated hydroxyaldehydes undergo two-electron oxidation to the corresponding hydroxy carboxylic acids at the elevated temperature (70°) as observed in the case of salicylaldehyde semicarbazone,

Manganese(III) sulphate oxidation of salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone in sulphuric acid-acetic acid medium could not be investigated because of the formation of the insoluble complex.

The experimental work suggests a clean method for the production of manganese(III) with high current efficiency, in aqueous sulphuric acid and aqueous acetic acid. The reactive species were different in these two system, the former contained the ionic forms, Mn^{3+} or MnOH^{2+} and the latter involved undecomposed $\text{Mn}(\text{OAc})_3$ or the acetato complex $\text{Mn}(\text{OAc})_4^-$. A second interesting point to emerge from this study was the consideration that the changes in the coordination environment of the oxidising species affect its redox behaviour. Manganese(III) sulphate in aqueous sulphuric acid with higher redox potential value for $\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}-\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$ couple of 1.52 V reacted more drastically. Manganese(III) acetate in aqueous acetic acid having a lower redox potential value of 1.16 V reacted in a sluggish way. The overall mechanism, number of electrons involved and the products formed in these two cases of electron transfer process were different.

Experimental

Manganese(III) sulphate in aqueous sulphuric acid and manganese(III) acetate in aqueous acetic acid were prepared by electrolytic method by employing lead and platinum electrodes respectively as described previously^{3,5}.

Semicarbazide hydrochloride (Loba-Chemie) was used after recrystallisation from pure ethanol. The semicarbazones of aldehydes and ketones (aceta-

TABLE 2—POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION OF SEMICARBAZIDE HYDROCHLORIDE AND SEMICARBAZONE DERIVATIVES IN ACETIC ACID-WATER MEDIUM AT 30°

Compd.	Range studied mg	Acetic acid % (v/v)	Electrons participating in reaction		Maximum error %
			Calcd.	Found $\pm$ SD ^a	
Semicarbazide hydrochloride	1.46–11.59	80	2	1.99 $\pm$ 0.04	1.50
	1.46–11.59	70	2	1.96 $\pm$ 0.05	–
	1.46–11.59	60	2	1.91 $\pm$ 0.05	–
Propionaldehyde semicarbazone	1.43–11.50	80	2	2.05 $\pm$ 0.04	1.27
Acetophenone semicarbazone	2.24–17.75	80	2	2.10 $\pm$ 0.04	1.42
Benzaldehyde semicarbazone	2.04–16.30	80	2	1.96 $\pm$ 0.04	1.53
Salicylaldehyde semicarbazone ^b	2.24–11.25	80	4	4.08 $\pm$ 0.06	1.20
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde semicarbazone	3.20–16.20	80	2	2.14 $\pm$ 0.05	1.80
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde semicarbazone ^b	3.40–16.80	80	2	1.85 $\pm$ 0.06	0.85

^aStandard deviation for 6 determinations. ^bAt 343 $\pm$ 2 K

ldehyde, propionaldehyde, benzaldehyde, 4-chlorobenzaldehyde, 4-nitrobenzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, acetophenone and benzophenone) were prepared by literature methods⁷. Glacial acetic acid (Glaxo-Special Quality, SQ) was further purified by refluxing with chromic oxide for 4 h followed by distillation. All other chemical used were of analytical grade.

Potentiometric titration : A Digisun 801 digital potentiometer with platinum-calomel electrode assembly was used throughout. Direct potentiometric titration of semicarbazide and semicarbazones, with manganese(III) sulphate in aqueous H₂SO₄ or H₂SO₄-HOAc mixture or with manganese(III) acetate in aqueous acetic acid (80%, v/v) took about 2–3 h. Therefore, back-titration with hydrazinium sulphate or hydroquinone was preferred. Manganese(III) sulphate in aqueous H₂SO₄-HOAc medium rapidly oxidised hydrazine sulphate through a reproducible one-electron transfer process. The redox reaction between hydroquinone and manganese(III) acetate in aqueous acetic acid medium was also extremely rapid and in this respect it resembled the reactions between ionic species in aqueous media¹⁶.

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A known volume of the reductant, semicarbazide hydrochloride of concentration 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ in H₂SO₄ medium of concentration 1.0–3.0 mol dm⁻³ was taken in a 100 cm³ beaker in which were placed a platinum indicator electrode and a standard calomel reference electrode (SCE) and the cell electromotive force E (V vs SCE) was noted. A mixture of aqueous H₂SO₄-HOAc of overall concentration 2.5 mol dm⁻³ and 20–50% (v/v) respectively, was employed for the preparation of semicarbazone solutions, as they are insoluble in aqueous medium. A known excess of manganese(III) sulphate of 0.01 mol dm⁻³ in aqueous H₂SO₄ of concentration 1–3 mol dm⁻³ or H₂SO₄-HOAc of appropriate composition, also containing known concentration of Mn^{II} as required for stability, was added from the microburette. The mixture was allowed to stand for ~0.5 h in a stoppered flask and the excess oxidant left over was back-titrated potentiometrically with 0.02 mol dm⁻³ hydrazinium sulphate in aqueous H₂SO₄ (1.0–3.0 mol dm⁻³) or in H₂SO₄-HOAc mixture of appropriate composition. In the case of manganese(III) acetate also a similar procedure was followed, but the medium was aqueous HOAc (80% v/v) and the back-titrant used was hydro-

quinone in aqueous acetic acid 80% (v/v). The titrations produced well defined sigmoid curves (Fig. 1a and b). The potential jump ranged from 400–600 mV per 0.1 cm³ of the added titrant at the end-point. Parallel titrations were carried out in which the excess oxidant left over was determined iodometrically.

Fig. 1(a). Potentiometric titration curves : (A) manganese(III) sulphate with hydrazinium sulphate, (B) semicarbazide and manganese(III) sulphate mixture, with hydrazinium sulphate, and (C) semicarbazide with manganese(III) sulphate; [manganese(III) sulphate] = 0.0099 mol dm⁻³, [hydrazinium sulphate] = 0.01124 mol dm⁻³, [semicarbazide hydrochloride] = 0.0098 mol dm⁻³; medium aqueous H₂SO₄ 5.0 mol dm⁻³, in temp = 25°.

Fig. 1(b) Potentiometric titration curves : (A) semicarbazide with manganese(III) acetate, (B) semicarbazide and manganese(III) acetate mixture, with hydroquinone, and (C) salicylaldehyde semicarbazone and manganese(III) acetate mixture with hydroquinone; [manganese(III) acetate] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³, [hydroquinone] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³, [semicarbazide hydrochloride] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, [salicylaldehyde semicarbazone] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³; medium aqueous HOAc (60%, v/v), and temp. = 25°.

Fig. 2(a). Absorption spectral profile of manganese(III) sulphate (0.0099 mol dm⁻³) recorded in the case of reductive titration with hydrazinium sulphate of concentration 0.01124 mol dm⁻³ in aqueous H₂SO₄ of overall concentration 2.5 mol dm⁻³ at 25°. curves shown with increasing percent reduction : (A) 0, (B) 38.22, (C) 54.55, (D) 69.45 and (E) 83.67%.

Fig. 2(b) Absorption spectral profile of manganese(III) sulphate from the mixture of semicarbazide hydrochloride (5.0 cm³ of 0.00098 mol dm⁻³) and manganese(III) sulphate (15.0 cm³ of 0.0099 mol dm⁻³), back-titrated with hydrazinium sulphate (0.01124 mol dm⁻³) in aqueous H₂SO₄ of overall concentration 2.5 mol dm⁻³; curves shown with increasing percent reduction : (F) 0, (G) 12.13, (H) 26.90, (I) 44.45 and (J) 66.23%.

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